

D1.3 Report of Stakeholders Forum 2021 including recommendations to the 1+MG Working Groups

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1. Executive Summary

Gaining the trust of patients, healthcare practitioners, research participants and society at large is paramount for data sharing in genomics and health. This requires involving different stakeholders to take into consideration different national contexts, as well as cultural and societal differences to build informed policies and implement genomics practices in health and research. To this end, the B1MG WP1 efforts are geared towards increasing the engagement, awareness and alignment of the different stakeholders involved in the genomics-based research and healthcare landscape within Europe. This involves bringing together and aligning efforts between the scientific and technical communities, international initiatives, and projects as well as national healthcare and research systems.

As a part of the WP1 tasks, this report describes the online Stakeholder Forum (SF) that was conducted on the 17th of November 2021 (SF 2021). The primary role of this SF was to **strengthen the alignment of B1MG stakeholders with the 1+MG initiative**. In particular, the central theme of the SF was the **1+MG Trust Framework**. This framework brings together the specific recommendations, guidelines and best practices that can be used to realise the 1+MG vision. Its core components are related to **ELSI and data governance** aspects, **data standards** for quality and interoperability in genomics data access and to the **infrastructure** components for cross-border access to genomics and related health data.

The SF 2021 brought together over **280 members from the various stakeholder communities** registered on the B1MG Stakeholder portal in a full day virtual meeting. The morning session introduced the different elements of the 1+MG Trust Framework and set the stage for the day. The afternoon session was split across six parallel sessions, where the components of the Trust Framework were explored from the perspective of use cases. While four of these sessions included the 1+MG disease use cases - Rare disease (WG8), Cancer (WG9), Common and Complex disease (WG10) and Infectious disease (WG11), two sessions gathered recommendations for 1+MG from the perspective of Industry (WG7) and the Genome of Europe (WG12). Throughout the day, the attendees engaged in specifically evaluating the common pitfalls and gathering recommendations around ELSI, data standards, and infrastructural requirements, which they confirmed are the three priority aspects to cover in the 1+MG Trust Framework.

The SF has proven to be an excellent instrument to capture the broad expert input from a large group of stakeholders to formulate recommendations to strengthen the work towards realising the 1+MG ambitions. Holding this meeting virtually gave the benefits that many stakeholders could join and participate at this early stage in the project. This report describes the various sessions and summarises the recommendations to 1+MG. The recommendations have been shared with colleagues in the 1+MG working groups on ELSI, standards and infrastructure soon after the SF and have since been taken up by these teams together with the coordination team to seed the design of the further roadmap for the 1+MG working groups.

2. Contribution towards project objectives

With this deliverable, the project has reached or the deliverable has contributed to the following objectives/key results:

	Key Result No and description	Contributed
Objective 1 Engage local, regional, national and European stakeholders to define the requirements for cross-border access to genomics and personalised medicine data	1. B1MG assembles key local, national, European and global actors in the field of Personalised Medicine within a B1MG Stakeholder Coordination Group (WP1) by M6.	Yes
	2. B1MG drives broad engagement around European access to personalised medicine data via the B1MG Stakeholder Coordination Portal (WP1) following the B1MG Communication Strategy (WP6) by M12.	Yes
	3. B1MG establishes awareness and dialogue with a broad set of societal actors via a continuously monitored and refined communications strategy (WP1, WP6) by M12, M18, M24 & M30.	Yes
	4. The open B1MG Summit (M18) engages and ensures that the views of all relevant stakeholders are captured in B1MG requirements and guidelines (WP1, WP6).	Yes
Objective 2 Translate requirements for data quality, standards, technical infrastructure, and ELSI into technical specifications and implementation guidelines that captures European best practice	Legal & Ethical Key Results	
	1. Establish relevant best practice in ethics of cross-border access to genome and phenotypic data (WP2) by M36	N/A
	2. Analysis of legal framework and development of common minimum standard (WP2) by M36.	N/A
	3. Cross-border Data Access and Use Governance Toolkit Framework (WP2) by M36.	N/A
	Technical Key Results	
	4. Quality metrics for sequencing (WP3) by M12.	N/A
	5. Best practices for Next Generation Sequencing (WP3) by M24.	N/A
	6. Phenotypic and clinical metadata framework (WP3) by M12, M24 & M36.	N/A
	7. Best practices in sharing and linking phenotypic and genetic data (WP3) by M12 & M24.	N/A
	8. Data analysis challenge (WP3) by M36.	N/A
Infrastructure Key Results		
9. Secure cross-border data access roadmap (WP4) by M12 & M36.	N/A	
10. Secure cross-border data access demonstrator (WP4) by M24.	N/A	

Objective 3 Drive adoption and support long-term operation by organisations at local, regional, national and European level by providing guidance on phased development (via the B1MG maturity level model), and a methodology for economic evaluation	1. The B1MG maturity level model (WP5) by M24.	N/A
	2. Roadmap and guidance tools for countries for effective implementation of Personalised Medicine (WP5) by M36.	N/A
	3. Economic evaluation models for Personalised Medicine and case studies (WP5) by M30.	N/A
	4. Guidance principles for national mirror groups and cross-border Personalised Medicine governance (WP6) by M30.	N/A
	5. Long-term sustainability design and funding routes for cross-border Personalised Medicine delivery (WP6) by M34.	N/A

3. Methods

3.1 Methodology

B1MG WP1 facilitates the engagement of stakeholders in the field of genomics-based health in the B1MG project and 1+MG initiative. The priority of the overall stakeholder engagement process is to involve key stakeholders (or their recommendations) in the essential workstreams organised as part of the B1MG Work Packages (WPs) and their corresponding 1+MG Working Groups (WGs). The stakeholders are (experts of) organisations of a variable nature and scope, and B1MG chooses to organise their involvement at multiple levels. Key persons representing identified stakeholders that are engaged and interested in the 1+MG initiative are invited to register through the Stakeholder Portal to be informed about the work in the B1MG work packages and to be involved in the expert layer of the 1+MG initiative as appropriate.

To facilitate this engagement, WP1, along with the leads from B1MG WPs/1+MG WGs, co-organises SF meetings that are held once per year, to discuss the progress in the project and 1+MG initiative with a broad set of stakeholders. Feedback received from stakeholders through these meetings is used to inform and shape work and decision making in the B1MG project.

Format

Due to the ongoing Covid19 pandemic and to ensure maximum participation, the meeting was organised virtually.

Agenda

The agenda (Annex 1) was structured to receive feedback and recommendations on this framework from across all use cases.

The morning session consisted of an overview from the B1MG project, where participants gave feedback on the proof-of-concept of the data infrastructure for managing genomics datasets and set out the 1+MG Trust Framework to be more widely adopted. It began with an introduction of the Trust Framework that has been developed in the 1+MG initiative with support of B1MG to bring together the specific recommendations, guidelines and best practices that will allow cross-border access to genomic health datasets in Europe. This included three sessions delving deeper into the three key aspects of the Trust Framework - ELSI aspects, data standards and data quality aspects, and infrastructural aspects respectively. The morning session was concluded with a special presentation on public trust and engagement and the challenges in implementation of genomics in healthcare.

The afternoon session consisted of six parallel online workshops related to the 1+MG Use Case Working Groups (Rare Diseases, Cancer, Common & Complex Diseases, Infectious Diseases, Genome of Europe & Industry). Each parallel workshop took on a specific use case with the goal to provide a list of recommendations that could be adopted in the work processes of each WG/WP from the use case perspective. These workshops began with presentations from experts and across initiatives in these fields related to the 1+MG goals. This was then followed by discussions on the alignment between stakeholders and partner projects, as well as the recommendations (from Use Case perspective) to be adopted in the development of B1MG/1+MG efforts regarding the aspects of the trust framework.

Target audience

Attendees invited included all involved in the B1MG project, WG leads, all registrants to the B1MG/1+MG stakeholder portal and B1MG partner projects. Participants were also drawn from key stakeholders from the community whose interaction could create a cross-sectoral, highly relevant and dynamic discussion forum. These included patients, healthcare professionals, decision makers, patient and citizen organisations, and European umbrella organisations representing interest groups and associations actively engaged in the field of Personalised Medicine.

3.2 Relationship with other WPs

The SF meeting has been organised to address topics (pink labels in Figure) and allow direct involvement of most of the working groups in 1+MG and work packages in B1MG, as summarised in the figure below. The green icons represent B1MG work packages and related Working groups addressing technical/infrastructural aspects of the 1+MG initiative, with the proposed three key topics of the 1+MG Trust Framework highlighted in bold. The blue icons represent the 1+MG Working groups addressing use case aspects of the 1+MG initiative, including the perspective of industry involvement and the establishment of the Genome of Europe reference dataset proposed as part of the 1+MG endeavours.

4. Description of work accomplished

4.1 Preparatory work and scope of session:

The B1MG consortium regards stakeholder engagement as a crucial activity and facilitates interaction between all active stakeholders in the European genomics-based health field. To this end, B1MG strives to have a strong representation from patient and citizen organisations, specialists and clinicians, scientists, HTA bodies and projects, pharmaceutical, diagnostic and ICT industry, European research infrastructures, EU joint actions, international project consortia and standardising bodies, and ELSI specialists amongst other. These stakeholder groups include members from signatory countries of the 1+MG initiative and at the European level. The key to successful and effective engagement with such a broad range of stakeholders is the generation of relevant recommendations to support decision making in relation to the areas of work of the B1MG and 1+MG workstreams.

4.2.1 Deliverable scope

SF2021 was centred around the 1+MG Trust Framework. The goal was to provide a common platform where elements of this framework could be introduced and discussed with participating stakeholders, as well as partner projects. It would support strengthening the use-case working groups; their interaction with/involvement in B1MG and 1+MG initiative; and increase alignment between the efforts of the B1MG stakeholders and the efforts of (potential) partner projects. The aim was to gather recommendations from the perspective of each use case to be used to guide the future efforts of the B1MG project and 1+MG initiative.

4.2.2 Key objectives of the SF2021

The Key objectives of the SF were threefold:

- Introduce the Trust Framework to B1MG/1+MG Stakeholders
- Align stakeholders and Partner Projects around the Trust Framework
- Generate recommendations on the Trust Framework from a use case and stakeholder perspective to be included in future work

4.2 General outcome:

A general overview of the outcome of the SF2021 is as follows:

- Number of attendees: 281
- Diversity of stakeholder groups represented by attendees (see pie-chart below):
 - Academia 49%
 - Healthcare 16%
 - Policy/Government 23%
 - Citizen 2%
 - Industry 1%
 - Other 8%

- Broad country representation (see pie-chart below):

- Diverse fields of expertise:

Participants represented a diverse array of fields of expertise, illustrative of the broad expertise base of the 1+MG initiative represented in the SF2021 meeting. **Collectively, the attendees invested 1068 expert hours during the day.**

- Bioinformatics, Genomics, health informatics, molecular biology etc.
- Data Infrastructure, Policy, Project management, Law
- Cancer, Rare disease, clinical genetics, epidemiology, precision genomics

4.3 Morning session

4.3.1 Introduction to B1MG , the 1+MG initiative and the 1+MG Trust Framework

Chair: Serena Scollen, ELIXIR Hub (WP5 - Coordination)

Link to [Slides](#)

Time: 1000 - 1005 CET

To set the stage, the morning session began with giving the participants an introduction to the B1MG project. This included discussing the aim of the forum, giving the background on the B1MG project, its relation to the 1+MG initiative, and key updates. Discussion focused on the aim of the B1MG project to create legal guidance, best practices and recommendations to develop an infrastructure that will enable the commitment of 22 EU Member States, Norway and UK to give cross-border access to one million sequenced genomes by 2022 (1+ Million Genomes Initiative). Key updates on the activities undertaken by the B1MG project were expanded upon.

- Development of stakeholder portal and stakeholder engagement activities undertaken by WP1
- Capacity building efforts carried through three country visits to exchange ideas and foster creative solutions for using genomic data in healthcare and development of a maturity level model to understand the maturity of the adoption of genomic data in diverse healthcare systems undertaken by WP5.
- Development of learning framework of National Mirror Groups (NMG) undertaken by WP6

The session concluded with gathering through Mentimeter questions general opinions from participating stakeholders on their idea of what a trust framework for 1+MG should cover and support. This brought forward various aspects such as collaboration, transparency, data, governance, access, interoperability, sharing, citizens, guidelines, amongst others (see image).

4.3.2 ELSI Aspects of the Trust Framework

Speaker: Regina Becker (University of Luxembourg - UniLu, LU) - 1+MG WG2/ B1MG WP2

[Slides](#)

This presentation focused on one of the three components of the Trust Framework- Ethical, Legal and Social Issues (ELSI) and data governance aspects. It reflected the efforts of B1MG WP2 in developing ELSI compliant practices for cross-border sharing of genomic data. What is meant by data governance, how data can be included under the 1+MG by ensuring that data is ethically and legally compliant, meets the conditions for submission and outlines the responsibilities of collecting this data were topics discussed during this session.

Topics discussed include:

- Best practices to make data accessible under the initiative requires defining who is accessing it, how and for what purpose
- Establishing procedures to ensure data access is efficient and compliant with these conditions/best practices
- Specific principles to guide the data governance policies within 1+MG:
 - to aim for 1+MG as a homogenous cohort to users;
 - respect the autonomy of countries, as well as the providers, subjects and users of data;
 - use IT to provide the flexibility of tagging data with ELSI related metadata;
 - ensuring the minimum requirements for participation in 1+MG foster the incorporation of EU norms into national norms
- Exploring the case of incidental findings to discuss concerns such as consent and the legitimacy of data processing procedures.
- Specifically, consent requirements were identified for 1+MG to evaluate whether research includes vulnerable subjects, secondary use of data, and a foreseeable need to re-contact physicians and data subjects.

The session concluded with a set of questions to be discussed during the afternoon breakout sessions:

1. Where will be the focus of activities - research or healthcare?
2. Is it possible to foresee the future needs for secondary use?
3. Is it possible to go back to the data subjects?

4.3.3 Data standards and data quality aspects

Speaker: Jeroen Belien VUMC, NL (B1MG WP3)

[Slides](#)

This session focused on the second component of the 1+MG Trust Framework - data standards and data quality aspects. The speaker presented the efforts of WP3 in translating requirements for data quality and standards for both genomic and clinical/phenotype into technical specifications and implementation guidelines that capture European best practices. The speaker identified the lack of standards for sequencing, nomenclature of quality metrics and their application across different laboratories, specifically in the context of Next Generation Sequencing of human genomes or exomes. Challenges to using existing clinical and phenotypic

information include incomplete, unstructured and heterogenous data, available across different systems, and recorded in local languages. The speaker outlined the work of B1MG WP3 in connecting WG4 and WG12 of the 1+MG initiative and establishing sequencing standards for the Genome of Europe.

4.3.4 Infrastructure aspects

Speakers: Tommi Nyronen / Dylan Spalding (ELIXIR Finland) - B1MG WP4

[Slides](#)

This presentation outlined the efforts of B1MG towards designing the federated secure cross border technical infrastructure key to the 1+MG initiative. The speaker discussed the progress in developing interoperability standards, as well as design-led secure services, promoting global standards for authorised access and increasing European capacity to manage sensitive data. The proof of concept developed using synthetic data in the rare disease use case was presented. The five functionalities of data discovery, reception, storage and interfaces, access management and data processing for the technical infrastructure required for the 1+MG initiative were then discussed along with exemplary tools and services developed/available to facilitate the secure sharing of data across borders. These included Beacon V1 and Matchmaker Exchange for data discoverability, ELIXIR-AAI and Resource entitlement management system (REMS) for data access management, and Federated EGA technology for storage and interfaces.

4.3.5 1+MG initiative: EC's perspective, role and support - European Commission

Speaker: Szymon Bielecki DG-CNECT

[Slides](#)

The objective of this session was to highlight the motivations driving the 1+MG initiative and the role of the European commission in enabling the genomic data sharing landscape. The speaker described the 1+MG initiative as an effort to connect healthcare, research and public health, through connecting data across the EU to increase understanding of the biology of diseases, develop new treatments, guide prevention plans, and influence public health policy. This initiative aligns with other aspects of the EU priorities such as the European Health Data space (EHDS), Artificial intelligence (AI), open data, Europe's beating cancer plan. The role of the EC in 1+MG is through interest and support expressed from CNECT, RTD, SANTE. The EC facilitates dialogue between the member states and with external stakeholders. The EC offers operational support through the 1+MG Group Secretariat (CNECT). The EC provides funding to support the coordination of 1+MG through B1MG (Coordination and Support Action), R&I actions through Horizon Europe, Digital Europe, EHDS actions, public health, pandemic preparedness through EU4Health and Genome of Europe amongst other actions. The EC also supports the development of legislation such as for EHDS, data governance, AI and cybersecurity.

4.3.6 Public trust and engagement: challenges for genomics and its implementation in health care

Speaker: Carla van El, VU Amsterdam

[Slides¹](#)

This presentation highlighted the integral role of citizens and the importance of public trust in realising the vision of personalised healthcare. The speaker described key requirements for building citizen trust in personalised healthcare - increasing awareness on the benefits, as well as challenges of genomic medicine; safe and trusted institutions to handle their personal data; and aligning health decisions to their personal values. Building this trust requires engaging with citizens and empowering them to be actively involved in shaping the policies and legislation around genomic medicine. European initiatives geared at engaging with citizens to facilitate the genomic data landscape were discussed.

4.4 Afternoon Session: Breakouts

Time: 13:00 to 15:00 CET

The afternoon session was organised into six parallel breakout sessions. Each session centred on a specific 1+MG use case.

1. Rare diseases (WG8)
2. Cancer (WG9)
3. Common and complex diseases (WG10)
4. Infectious disease (WG11)
5. Industry engagement (WG7)
6. Genome of Europe (WG12)

The objective of the breakout sessions was to evaluate common issues and pitfalls and to gather recommendations for best practices and further actions for the 1+MG initiative around ELSI, Data standards and infrastructure from the use case perspective. Each session consisted of several short presentations by representatives from the working groups, and/or from partner projects relevant to the work streams of the 1+MG Working Groups. This was followed by a discussion among the participants of the session. The outcome of each discussion was organised and presented as recommendations to B1MG, as much as possible on the three aspects of the 1+MG Trust Framework.

4.4.1 Rare diseases (WG8)

Chair: Marco Tartaglia (1+MG WG8, Ospedale Pediatrico Bambino Gesù (OPBG), IT)

Co-chair: Sergi Beltran Agullo (CNAG-CRG, ES)

[Slides²](#)

Speakers:

- ERN-ITHACA and the Rare Disease landscape in Europe - Klea Vyshka (Robert Debré University Hospital, Paris, FR)
- The Screen4Care EU-IMI project: aims and vision - Alessandra Ferlini (S. Anna University Hospital & University of Ferrara, Ferrara, IT)
- GenoMed4ALL - Federico Álvarez (Universidad Politécnica de Madrid, Madrid, ES)

¹https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1Ijlx_aflt2FABkFOpjX5LTciccYdH2fnZtHwPxOf1gM/edit#slide=id.p1

²<https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1JsvLdHABDaf1j0PkmcgPTFpjEWn8wGIR/edit#slide=id.p1>

- EJP RD (Annalisa Landi, Fondazione per la Ricerca Farmacologica Gianni Benzi Onlus, Bari, IT)
- Solve-RD - Lisenka Vissers (Radboud University Medical Center, Nijmegen, NL)

B1MG WP2, 3 or 4 representatives:

WP2 - Davit Chokochvili (UNILU, LU)

WP3 - Domenico Coviello (UCSC, IT)

WP4 - Johan Viklund (NBIS, SE), Sergi Beltran (CNAG-CRG, ES), Domenico Coviello (UCSC, IT)

Number of participants: 27

The focus of this breakout session was to formulate recommendations for B1MG from the RD use case perspective along three aspects of the 1+MG Trust Framework. The session included presentations from relevant international initiatives in RD - European Reference Network (ERN) - Ithaca, Screen4Care project by EU-Innovative Medicines Initiative; GenoMed4ALL; and EJP-RD. The session highlighted typical cases in RD where patients:

- may have a known genetic disorder but not molecularly solved (genetic heterogeneity);
- may be affected by a likely genetic disorder awaiting for the identification of the molecular cause;
- may be undiagnosed and waiting for clinical & molecular classification;
- may show phenotypic variation associated with variants in the same gene.

To this end, the 1+MG initiative will increase knowledge of the genetic make-up of RD, enhance diagnostic capabilities, improve understanding on phenotypic variability, and contribute to more informed clinical decision making.

ELSI	
Gaps/Challenges	Recommendations
Diverse definitions of common concepts and terminology such as ‘secondary use of data’ and ‘incidental findings’ that presented challenges in navigating ELSI in their research.	Harmonise definitions across EU projects and initiatives and align with EJP-RD terminology.
The need for flexible informed consent forms that can be used within the EU for different purposes.	EJP-RD has a flexible Informed Consent Form (ICF) for the ERNs which is research oriented. The ERNs can adapt this IC template to their needs, but will not necessarily include secondary use of data or genomics data.

Data standards

Gaps/Challenges	Recommendations
Increasing data on Whole Exome Sequencing (WES)	Define data standards for WES data in addition to WGS
Other data types besides phenome and genome should be considered (e.g. data from EHRs, MRIs, availability of samples in biobanks)	Consider collecting which other data types should be included in the IT and issue recommendations on standards.

Infrastructure	
Gaps/ Challenges	Recommendations
Connecting 1+MG IT and datasets to other international initiatives	Develop bi-directional data discovery mechanisms connecting to other resources or IT networks (e.g. MatchMaker Exchange nodes outside Europe).
Analysis of multiple genomic variants (oligogenic inheritance), haplotypes or the full genomic data from individual records	Include functionalities in 1+MG IT to cater to this need
Inclusion of additional data types beyond genomics and phenomics might be relevant for RDs	Evaluate how to include other data types that can be used for analysis

The group also put forward certain general questions/recommendations for 1+MG:

1. There exists a large collection of WES data from “unique” patients/diseases. How can these be included in the 1+MG infrastructure?
2. Is the approach taken by B1MG to define IT, adequate? Consult the different national/regional undiagnosed disease programmes to understand their data sharing practices - data standards, data types, ELSI, amongst others which could be instrumental in informing the 1+MG WGs.
3. Define the expected timeline to have access to the federated Infrastructure and be able to perform individual queries.
4. Consider a single access path for RD diagnosis and novel pathogenic gene identification as research and healthcare are often done in conjunction in this case.

5. RD data is longitudinal to capture changes in MRI at different ages, for example. So B1MG should evaluate how ELSI and IT can accommodate such data.
6. The infrastructure should in the future enable artificial intelligence.

4.4.2 Cancer (WG9)

Chair: Giovanni Tonon (ACC/HSR, IT)

Co-chair: Nina Habermann (B1MG WP1 EMBL)

[Slides](#)³

Speakers:

- GHGA: Towards a German Research Infrastructure for Genome Medicine - Jan Korbel (EMBL, DE)
- EuCanCAN & ICGC Argo - David Torrents (BSC, ES)

B1MG WP2, 3 or 4 Representatives:

WP2 - Regina Becker (UNILU, LU)

WP3 - Michela Riba (HSR, IT), Michela Tebaldi (IRCCS, IT), Jeroen Belien (VUmc, NL)

WP4 - Tommi Nyrönen (CSC, FI)

Number of participants: 44

The focus of this breakout session was to formulate recommendations for B1MG from the Cancer use case perspective along three aspects of the 1+MG trust framework. The session included presentations from GHGA: Towards a German Research Infrastructure for Genome Medicine, and EuCanCAN & ICGC Argo. The presentations brought forward the typical problems in oncology research and efforts to address them. Discussions included the challenges posed by language and communication across different data sets. Other challenges included the legal and technological complexities posed by different layers of federation, as well as the cultural shift towards open science.

For the ELSI aspect of the Trust Framework, the group identified key challenges/gaps along with recommendations for addressing them:

ELSI	
Gaps/ Challenges	Recommendations

³https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1y4_FRbWLNhaDDwmbDI4Kw5ZWYqorhNCzulLkAMt0B-0/edit#slide=id.g10062849a3a_5_0

Need to provide guidance for re-consent	To assess the feasibility of doing so with guidance from WP2 and WP5
Define a workflow to get access to the data, at the institutional and national level, and be able to perform a data protection impact assessment for the workflow	Provide funding to support the capacity and expertise of WG5 needed to define this workflow.
Since cancer incidence varies across Europe, based on exposure and variable genetics, data linkage is required, but it is challenging and potentially intrusive.	Develop a European mandate to define and use appropriate identifiers, which are legally acceptable.

Data Standards	
Gaps/Challenges	Recommendations
Member states have difficulties to agree on ontology. Cost for licenses are a hurdle.	SNOMED base licence will be supported by EC (60%) in upcoming years; WG9 is working alongside WG3 on defining the most suitable ontologies (considering also the level of details that each platform provides).
ICD is often used for different purposes (e.g. statistics) and can be mapped back to SNOMED but those mappings need to be maintained.	Mapping needs to be maintained: process should be part of the framework: action for WG9 & WG3
Cancer has longitudinal aspect (multiple data points in time)	To address the longitudinal aspect (cohort data), we may need to include proper measurements of disease progression and relapse definition

Infrastructure	
Gaps/Challenges	Recommendations

Lack of a standard cancer data analysis software that can be used	WG9 action ongoing, to review the available options and provide recommendations
Explore Cancer data management tools for cancer	WG9 action ongoing, to review the available options and provide recommendations
Synthetic dataset for cancer genomes	1+MG WG4 should work with WG5 & WG10 to develop this reference data set

4.4.3 Common and Complex diseases (WG10)

Chair: Andres Metspalu (UT, EE)

Co-chair: Serena Scollen (B1MG, ELIXIR Hub)

Speakers:

- PerMed project in Estonia - Lili Milani (UT, EE)
- 1+MG synthetic genome data simulation project - Tero Hiekkalinna (UH, FI)

B1MG WP2, 3 or 4 representatives:

WP2 - Adrian Thorogood (UNILU, LU)

WP3 - Laima Ambrozaityte (VULSK, LT)

WP4 - Dylan Spalding (CSC, FI)

Number of participants: 21

The aim of this session was to list recommendations to 1+MG/ B1MG WGs/WPs from the perspective of infectious disease as a use case. Presentations included COVID 19 Data Portal; BY Covid project; ISIDore project, and the EC FAIR Covid-19 data workshops. The session targeted experts in virology/pathogens, population health researchers, bioinformaticians, policy makers and infrastructures. The recent pandemic exposed the gaps and niches in the infectious disease data landscape, particularly the problems of connectivity, fragmented data, and sufficient capacity for storage with the aim of linking human and pathogens data. The need to maintain an open portal for sharing different types of data such as viral, host, expression, proteins and other sequencing data was acknowledged. Challenges around urgently navigating ELSI, data standards and infrastructural requirements were recognised and recommendations to do so were offered.

ELSI

Gaps and pitfalls and considerations	Recommendations
Health data is different for each common disease. For eg. Individual SNP and longitudinal health data mainly used for research/GWAS, whereas summary statistics are valuable in healthcare/policy context.	There is a need for a plan to manage and share data and a consent/transparency template to suit these needs.
Return of risk score to the “healthy patient”	As this is not a diagnosis, education tools are needed to deal with this contingency. Recontact covered by lightweight consent.
Direct access to individual data may not be needed or even scientifically/technical possible in this use case (millions of records).	Is remote (indirect) access feasible for many uses? Is there a need for access rights and funding (compute) for cross-border researchers?
Future integration of genotyping into public health screening programs - purpose limitation issues.	Consent that is simple but feeds “healthy patient” data into ongoing research.
Are minority groups across/within countries being left out?	Need to consider how to provide healthcare to all

Data standards	
Gaps and pitfalls	Recommendations
Heterogeneity in data collection practices.	Standardise data collection. Use same input data for each disease, need standards for lifestyle data, use standards to combine data sets that have been collected in a different way,

Diverse definitions and analytical tools	Harmonise definitions and analytical tools by setting up dictionary to capture ways to harmonise data so these are shared
Information is needed for each data receiver	Data dictionary is useful to obtain information
How do you use data that has already been collected	Build repositories - helps with secondary use; use of mapping tools

For the infrastructure aspect of the Trust Framework, the group identified key challenges/gaps along with recommendations for addressing them:

Infrastructure	
Gaps and pitfalls	Recommendations
Distributed analysis to different data hubs to generate PRS must be supported	Capability to run common analysis tools based on common input sets such as disease loci
Need extensive harmonisation of lifestyle / phenotypic data	Support extensive sharing of rich phenotype data - encourages harmonisation by experts. Infrastructure must be FAIR - both in cost and FAIRification
How will data be returned to the participant? How to support participants' access to genetic data	Need for data communication / visualisation tools Support range of output / communication tools.
Curation and maintenance of the data - e.g. genetic / phenotype associations	Need experts to manage this

4.4.4 Infectious diseases (WG11)

Chair: Katja Kivinen (FIMM, FI)

Co-chair: Emanuela Oldoni (EATRIS-ERIC, NL)

[Slides⁴](#)

Speakers:

- COVID-19 Data Portal - Guy Cochrane (ENA)
- BY-COVID project - Katharina Lauer (ELIXIR Hub)
- ISIDOre project - Romain David (ERINHA, FR)
- EC FAIR Covid-19 data workshops - Lauren Maxwell (Heidelberg University, DL)

B1MG WP2, 3 or 4 representatives

WP2 - Mark Bale (Genomics England, UK)

WP3 - Alina Lupu (EC), Ulrika Hermansson (University of Gothenburg, SE)

WP4 - Ilkka Lappalainen (CSC, FI)

Number of participants: 24

The aim of this session was to identify common issues and gather recommendations for further actions in 1+MG and partner projects around ELSI, Data standards and Infrastructure from WG10 Common and Complex Diseases use case perspective. The session included presentations from The FinnGen study; PerMed project in Estonia, and the 1+MG synthetic genome data simulation project. The general discussion focused on the need to gather population sequence data to capture the maximum amount of genomic heterogeneity and use it for imputations. The importance of conducting SNP arrays; developing algorithms to accommodate genomics, as well as environmental and lifestyle risks; and using polygenic risk scores and pharmacogenomics data, was identified. The 1+MG initiative could enable this to identify populations with a high risk and facilitate large scale population based early intervention programmes to prevent common and complex disease.

ELSI	
Gaps/Challenges	Recommendations
It is difficult to reach a shared interpretation of ethical concerns	Different use cases/populations need to be considered differently

⁴https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1Ap4IYpVsmrzhqAn43IRNlx45NvjMy2hW89MezY_QPeU/edit#slide=id.g10062849a3a_5_0

GDPR-related issues	Providing a Code of conduct, review effects of GDPR on governance structures
Data and metadata sharing and interoperability take time and money, yet there is a lack of recognition associated with data curation and sharing	Work towards recognition of data sharing and additional funding for interoperability and metadata creation and sharing

Data standards	
Gaps/Challenges	Recommendations
Lack of harmonisation of standard data management practices across borders	Harmonisation and standardisation of data sharing and develop agreements on the minimum information for standards; Education of PhD & postdoc - raise awareness on the importance of good data production
Metadata are not routinely collected and lack standards	Build capacity in the use of community-developed standards; Work within related groups to develop metadata standards;
Lack of data description	Implement machine readable DMPs that collect data on components of FAIR

Infrastructure	
Gaps/Challenges	Recommendations
Fractured data production (human genomic, human healthcare, pathogen genomic & metadata)	For WG11, need to collect & link host with pathogen data which can be done by connecting relevant communities
Variable maturity level (between & within signatory states)	Resources to ensure all signatories will be able to participate
Data standards	Agreement on aspirational and minimum level (usable data vs optimal data model)
Data are linked to projects and it difficult to locate after the conclusion of the project	Need to locate the data using discipline specific platforms

The group also put forward certain general recommendations for 1+MG:

1. It is vital to ensure the collection of pathogen and human data and being able to link them. Recommendation to 1+MG to explore pathogen neutral tools, especially metagenomics as it is one of the key outcomes research offers to supplement public health surveillance.
2. Recommend 1+MG to extend support in generating and collecting data for other types of pathogens such as fungi and parasites.

4.4.5 Genome of Europe (WG12) - [minutes](#)⁵

Chair - André Uitterlinden (1+MG WG12, ErasmusMC, NL)

Co-chair - Ruben Kok (1+MG CG, B1MG WP1, DTL-Projects/Health-RI, NL)

[Slides](#)⁶

Speakers:

- WG12/GoE Presentation - AU
- ELSI aspects relevant to the GoE (SE)

B1MG WP2, 3 or 4 representatives:

WP2 - Signe Mezinska (BBMRI-LV, LV)

WP3 - Flavio Soares (SPMS, PT), Alfonso Valencia (BSC, ES)

WP4 - Frederik Coppens (VIB, BE), Heikki Lehväslaiho (CSC, FI)

No. of participants - 85

The goal of this session was to evaluate common issues, best practices and to gather recommendations for further actions in 1+MG and partner projects to establish the Genome of Europe (WG12). 1+MG Trust Framework aspects (ELSI, Data standards and Infrastructure) were also addressed.

André Uitterlinden presented the scope and ambitions to establish a collective and federated European Whole Genome reference collection based upon national population cohorts combined with clinical data, as national reference collections connected across Europe through 1+MG. The GoE dataset would form a globally unique collection capturing the genetic constellation of the entire European population. The ambition is to gather sequence information of at least 500.000 participating citizens. Based on population size, the WG12 team has proposed a certain minimal amount of records to individual countries as their national contribution to the GoE collection. André also touched on two typical projects run at Erasmus Medical Centre in Rotterdam (GOALL (Genotyping On ALL patients) and SENSE (societal use of genetic information)

⁵<https://docs.google.com/document/d/1VsQHCsRntZsWHFJ3wpxeoKxlt5969du0eUucc7mJZAs/edit>

⁶https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1WaLyvop4oPV-jfmw_z_Gg2yllAI8uuApL73IEw0ZsD0/edit#slide=id.g10062849a3a_5_0

to illustrate the value of having rich genetic information that has no disease bias. Only a minimal set of associated personal/health related data would be targeted to include in each record. Attendees were clearly interested in the chosen approach and wanted to understand how the GoE datasets would be realised and how it would fit the 1+MG process and infrastructure.

The role of WG12 has been to elaborate on the general approach towards realising this monumental federated GoE reference dataset in the coming years, including criteria for subject selection (involving minorities relevant to each country), data generation and associated personal (health) data and data protection. WG12 also works to identify possible angles (including funding routes) towards generating the data in the various countries, with an eye on comparability of the national collections.

The outcome of this session was a list of general recommendations on the approaches to realise the GoE reference collection, including aspects of the Trust Framework. Related to ELSI aspects, discussions specifically addressed ethical aspects of non-discrimination (securing the involvement of minorities) and how to include children. GoE requires understanding of the legal basis of the data (clinical vs mostly non-clinical cohorts) and associated consent. Related to data standards, a very minimal set of personal data elements is required as the basis, that can then be linked to further associated information for individual studies (many cohorts across Europe already have much broader data collections). Infrastructure-wise, the GoE collection will follow the overall 1+MG standards, while without a lot of associated phenotypic information there may also be a model to make the entire dataset available for research.

ELSI	
Gaps/Challenges	Recommendations
<p>Where is data coming from? Where will they primarily be used: 'Healthy' citizen-data generated outside healthcare. This means that a major part of the data will be generated in research. Primary use is research, secondary use is policy-making and in healthcare. What does that indicate in terms of its terms of use in research or in healthcare?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Reference Data coming from 'healthy' control population 2. Based upon population biobanks in many countries 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - GoE would like to engage with WG2 experts to define the legal context of these data, and what basic consent would fit best - Distinguish levels of consent and how they point to levels of use
<p>Specific issues in accessing minorities reference genomes and inclusion of minorities and children</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Attention to include ethnic minorities across Europe and how to 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - "Genetic non-discriminatory act" needed in all participating countries - 1+MG should include this in the minimal requirements

<p>deal with the fact that ethnicity can often not be recorded.</p> <p>2. Attention to involve children (underage)</p>	
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Data standards	
Gaps/Challenges	Recommendations
<p>Consideration for minimal data sets to be used for GoE</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Very minimal phenotypic dataset (Age, sex, biological gender) - Whether or not to include more data related to health brings forward different opinions. Linking such data can also be done later. - Ethnicity data is difficult to collect and locate and often against legislation 	<p>Define very minimal dataset and associated standard ontologies</p>

Infrastructure	
Gaps/Challenges	Recommendations
<p>Need to define the model: are we building a cohort to analyse/re-analyse or generate a big file that could be downloaded for variant calling?</p> <p>Different opinions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Without phenotypic data it would only be that big file that could be downloaded for variant calling 	<p>Evaluate the diverse possible models of use for GoE and how this would translate to infrastructure requirements (could progressively get more complex).</p>

<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Importance to provide controls for 'everything'- use cases have different requirements for infrastructure	
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4.4.6 Industry (WG 7)

Chair: Silja Elunurm (Estonian Ministry of Social Affairs, EE)

Co-chair: Merlijn van Rijswijk (B1MG WP1; DTL-Projects / Health-RI)

[Slides](#)⁷

Speakers:

- Introduction - Silja Elunurm (Estonian Ministry of Social Affairs, EE)
- Danny van Roijen (COCIR, BE)
- Wendy Maas (Roche Netherlands, NL)

B1MG WP2, 3 or 4 representatives:

WP2 - Olga Tzortzatou (BBMRI-GR, GR)

WP3 - Wei Gu (ELIXIR-LU, LU)

WP4 - Babita Singh (EMBL-EBI/EGA, UK)

No. of participants: 30

The goal of this session was to evaluate common issues, best practices and to gather recommendations for further actions in 1+MG and partner projects around ELSI, data standards and infrastructure from WG7 Industry use case perspective. Presentations included perspectives from the Estonian Biobank (Estonian Ministry of Social Affairs); European trade association Cocir; and pharmaceutical company Roche (Netherlands). The group identified that there are complex issues in genomics which cannot be solved by healthcare alone. The focus of the discussion was to identify why data skills are integral to realising personalised healthcare; the industry perspective on the important role of genomics; and the challenges in engaging the academic, research and industry sector in collaborating on genomic medicine and research.

The outcome of this session was a list of general recommendations on the gaps where industry could support 1+MG, as well as how 1+MG efforts could assist industry in furthering the common goal of personalised healthcare. The role of WG7 has been to establish the purpose of involving private actors in the 1+MG initiative. This session identified why there is a need to do so and how trust can be established between industry and the other stakeholders involved in 1+MG.

⁷https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1HKKS-U9nha3kyF6lzo7PWyuXmu7ZOvuiUHPKjENcbol/edit#slide=id.g10062849a3a_5_0

ELSI

In the context of ELSI, several concerns were raised during this session. The industry will ultimately need a federated data infrastructure (privacy by design) and there likely will be a citizen controlled data market (data owned by the patient). With respect to this, one of the concerns was around consent, where practical solutions are needed. Challenges of knowing what the consent has been generated for, the need for broad consent, the ethical committee's inclination towards small consents, and the difficulties of reconsenting when patients have been deceased or moved for instance, coupled with the administrative burden involved were recognised to make secondary use difficult. For data governance, concerns of who accesses the data, what is the procedure, what are they accessed for, clear description of procedures and responsibilities were also discussed. According to the group, immediate feedback to the patients was another primary concern which needed more attention. This raised further questions on the right to know and not know. The problem is that data is abstract, and hence it is difficult to imagine what is happening with it. The general public has difficulty in understanding Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning. We need to explain better what we are doing.

Suggestions to learn from local Citizen Science projects or patient-centric small scale projects were proposed. Efforts adopted by industry to improve public trust were also recommended. Publishing use cases, explaining the technology, expanding on how training of algorithms takes place and how this contributes to better health outcomes were offered as example efforts. The willingness of industry to share consent data, as well as use real world data from patients/citizens to improve treatments was discussed. The 1+MG initiative could be used to recruit patients for studies and to identify patients suitable for studies. Use cases on genomics data impact is important for building public trust, both generic as well as to the individual. There is a need to increase public awareness on technological possibilities and the impact this has on improving healthcare for eg. apps provide continuous feedback which is instrumental in this case.

Data standards

For the data standards aspect, the session offered other stakeholders to raise questions concerning the intention of industrial partners to be data providers, users, or both; the types of companies that could be data providers; the interests of companies as data users in secondary use of data for research, healthcare, policy development, quality management, amongst others. Efforts for industry to comply with common data standards (data model, ontology) and data integration systems/platforms, as well as ensure high quality data by making data FAIR and sharing it back with national databases were discussed, for instance in the case of Covid19 data. Recommendations to 1+MG included developing a continuous data flow, to get towards a learning based healthcare system and to use FAIR data points that can help in sharing data to other stakeholders without data leaving the organisation, and have data-visiting approaches.

Data infrastructure

In this context, the group identified that there are different commercial and non-commercial licensing options for software possible that could be used for genomics data sharing.

General recommendations from the group:

1. Industry involvement is crucial for putting (genomics) data into clinical practice and routine.

2. Industry is willing to co-create with academia, with regards to standards, access procedures, privacy by design, quality and interoperability.
3. Big changes in the healthcare system are taking place, and the industry is also willing to feed back data to (national) data repositories.
4. The need to combine personal/patient data to get to predictive and outcome based reimbursement systems and improve patient outcomes (partly beyond the scope of the project) on a country level

5. Results

5.1 Recommendations from Breakout sessions

Recommendations from the use case breakouts have been summarised per breakout below.

5.1.1 Rare disease

ELSI: There is a need to harmonise the definition of terms that define the different ELSI requirements of enabling cross-border genomic health data sharing. The recommendation is to link to other projects that have already handled these issues. Additionally, there is a need for flexible consent forms which require synergies with partner projects, for example EJP RD that has developed a consent form which can be used for research.

Data standards: There is a large amount of WES data that is unique and covers very rare conditions. As research and healthcare in the context of this use case are often done in conjunction, the use case needs could be better served with a single assessment pathway that deals with both aspects - research, as well as healthcare. For this, data standards need to be defined not only for WGS but also for WES data. These data standards should also include considerations for additional information such as MRI and biosamples that play an important role in the rare disease use case.

Infrastructure - Recommendations highlight the need for bidirectional links to improve success of identification of any matches between datasets from across databases covering rare disease data. The infrastructure should also provide means to analyse multiple genomic variants, as well as inclusion of additional data types.

5.1.2 Cancer (WG9)

ELSI - Recommendations to provide guidance for obtaining re-consent from participants regarding the reuse of their genomic data for secondary research. To be aligned with the efforts

of WP2 and WP5. The use case also requires defining the workflows for institutional and national access to data. This requires funding for training and gaining expertise on doing so.

Data standards - Recommendations from this use case highlight the need to agree on ontologies and gather funding for licences for data standards such as SNOMED. Additionally, they also put forward a need for practical data standards that are simple enough to be used by medics while including all required information.

Infrastructure - The group recognised the lack of consensus on software needed to analyse cancer data. There is a need to explore data management tools for cancer that will shape the genomic data sharing infrastructure. The recommendation is to work alongside WG4 (Ivo Gut) regarding synthetic genomes for cancer to address this gap.

5.1.3 Common complex diseases (WG10)

ELSI - Enabling this use case requires better data management and data sharing planning tools. It also requires the development of a lightweight consent form to re-contact patients. As direct access to individual data across borders may not be possible, there is a need to ascertain the feasibility of remote access to such data. Additionally, the use case warrants providing healthcare in an inclusive manner which is difficult since minority groups are often left out.

Data standards - The group recommends developing standards for data collection by using the same input for data for each disease. It highlights the need for a data dictionary to capture ways to harmonise data. Additionally, it raises the need for better standardisation of lifestyle/phenotypic data by striving for FAIR implementation across the health(-care) sector.

Infrastructure - The infrastructural requirements highlighted by this group were to address the need for common analysis tools to cater to different uses of polygenic risk scores. It also recommends the development of a FAIR-enabling infrastructure that will support future extensive harmonisation of lifestyle and phenotypic data. Additionally, the infrastructure needs to increase support for outreach and communication tools with respect to return of data to the participant. Another recommendation is to bring in experts to curate and maintain data for this use case.

5.1.4 Infectious disease (WG11)

ELSI - The group recognised the difficulty in arriving at a shared interpretation of ethical concerns across different populations and use cases. The infrastructure needs to address GDPR related issues such as providing a code of conduct and GDPR's effects on governance structures. The infrastructure needs to raise awareness on effort required for curating and sharing data and work towards gathering additional funding for interoperability and metadata creation and sharing.

Data standards - The group identifies challenges in the harmonisation of data sharing protocols across borders, the routine collection of metadata, and the lack of common standards for data description. They recommend developing agreements on the minimum standards for data sharing, building capacity in the use of community developed standards, implementing machine

readable DMPs, developing FAIR metadata standards by working within related groups, education of PhD and postdocs to raise awareness on good data production.

Infrastructure - The group recognised the challenge of fragmented data production in human genomic, human healthcare, pathogen genomic (meta)data. There is a variable maturity level between different signatory states. Additionally, they raised the hurdle of linking data across projects by making project related data findable after the conclusion of the projects. They recommend WG11 to collect and link host and pathogen data by connecting with relevant communities. They also recommend providing resources to ensure all signatories will be able to participate and agree on aspirational and minimal levels of data standards. They recommend making data findable in order to locate it through disciplinary platforms. Another need for B1MG to look into is the selection of pathogen-neutral tools to supplement public health surveillance.

5.1.5 Genome of Europe

ELSI - Since a large part of the data to be adopted in the Genome of Europe reference collection will be based on population cohorts and may therefore be generated outside healthcare, the group recommends to explore with WG/WP2 the legal basis of such data and how this affects the potential use in research and healthcare. Inclusion of minorities must be secured, based upon a system of non-discrimination by default (genetic non-discrimination approach), taking into account that ethnicity may not be recorded.

Data standards - 1+MG WG12 must explore how working with a minimal dataset associated with the recorded whole genome information can be done while keeping the possibility open for future deeper analysis. Standard ontologies are needed for the selected minimal data elements to maximise semantic interoperability.

Infrastructure - As the collective Genome of Europe dataset provides a basic reference dataset that can be used across research and healthcare for all diseases, the 1+MG infrastructure must be able to support a wide variety of analyses, growing in complexity with future deeper phenotypic data. It may be explored how the minimal dataset may be made available as a single big file for research purposes.

5.1.6 Industry

ELSI - Practical solutions are needed to record (re-)consent of data use and prevent administratively cumbersome procedures for secondary use of health data in public-private research and in internal innovation or product development processes. Generally, 1+MG could play a role in increasing public awareness on technological possibilities and the impact this will have on improving healthcare. Better information and education of the public will be required to support building public trust in the future broader use of Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning on personal (genomic) health data. The group recommends 1+MG to explore how it could assist in identifying patients suitable for (clinical) studies.

Data standards - Industry requires clarity on standards used and is willing to engage in processes towards standardisation. 1+MG may act as an aggregator to record community-based standards and is proposed to deliver clear recommendations to implement common data standards for data (data models, ontologies) and for data integration systems/platforms.

Data infrastructure - Apart from the legal aspects, industry notes that shared data access may not need physical moving of data outside firewalls. It is recommended that the 1+MG will facilitate data-visiting approaches to help shared data access without data leaving the organisation.

General recommendations - Participants recommend to involve industry more closely, which will be crucial for putting (genomics) data into routine clinical practice. 1+MG is recommended to regard industry as a partner to co-create with academia, with regards to standards, access procedures, privacy by design, quality and interoperability. Industry can also be a data provider: companies are also willing to feed back certain consented data to (national) data repositories. Generally, by facilitating personal health/patient data, 1+MG could contribute to predictive and outcome-based reimbursement systems and improve patient outcomes.

6. Discussion

The online SF 2021 has been designed to facilitate stakeholder interaction around 1+MG progress in general and in particular around crucial workstreams arranged for in the 1+MG framework (and supporting B1MG Work Packages). Over 280 participants from a broad range of backgrounds, expertise areas and nationalities were involved in the plenary sessions in the morning and feedback in the afternoon, and in the six use case break outs in the afternoon.

The 1+MG Trust Framework was the binding topic in the discussions organised from the perspective of use cases. By arranging for attendance of experts from the 1+MG working groups/B1MG work packages on ELSI, Standards and Infrastructure aspects in the use case breakouts, any possible unclarities could be addressed immediately and recommendations formulated in such a way that the ELSI, Standards and Infrastructure teams could evaluate best how to weave these recommendations into their respective roadmaps.

The emerging 1+MG Trust Framework has thus been put to the test for the first time during this meeting, and it is reassuring to note that the collective stakeholders confirm the B1MG-prioritised elements of ELSI and data governance, standards and infrastructure design as most essential for a 1+MG Trust Framework. The meeting also was the first event to present such a broad overview of 1+MG in its general design, and discuss its roadmap towards facilitating cross-border access of genomics based health data from the perspective of all use cases, with involved stakeholders.

The overall structure of the day allowed us to cover multiple perspectives on 1+MG: general update from the coordination layer, expert presentations on the ELSI, Standards and Infrastructure approaches, expression of support by the European Commission as well as a keynote contribution on aspects of public trust. Subsequently, in the parallel sessions, the Trust Framework was discussed and recommendations formulated from the perspective of individual use cases. The sessions on the Genome of Europe and Industry Engagement also provided more general recommendations to 1+MG.

From these different use cases, it is clear that 1+MG will have to facilitate multiple forms of use of genomics and associated health(care) data in the future. Generally, stakeholders advise to bring the practice of data use in primary care and in research and innovation closer to each other, growing to support a practice of data-enabled learning health care in the various fields. Another generic aspect 1+MG should facilitate is to raise awareness across Europe on the importance of curating and sharing health-related data and work towards interoperability and metadata creation and sharing.

In order to ultimately bring genomics into healthcare (and prevention) stakeholders advise 1+MG to work with its national initiatives on building public trust in genomics data sharing. This point was clearly made by keynote speaker Carla van El in the morning, and echoed in the afternoon during the industry session. Generally, stakeholders raise the importance of building public trust to contribute personal (genomics) data to national collections that can ultimately be collectively used on a European scale.

With respect to ELSI aspects, and despite differences in research and clinical practice stakeholders from the various use case communities all call for a common approach to capture citizen/patient consent (and also re-consent) for broader use of genomics health data outside direct primary care. As such, 1+MG requires an ELSI-enabled infrastructure that is GDPR-compliant by design and makes it easy for contributors and users to connect to drive the design and implementation of genomics-based personalised medicine and health strategies across Europe.

Discussing the various needs towards data standards, it is clear that 1+MG will have to take other genomics data types in scope as well (WES, arrays). While each domain will have to work with (and therefore design) domain-specific ontologies, there is also a call to harmonise disease ontologies in such a way that they will have maximal overlapping data elements. This is important to realise data interoperability across 1+MG communities and further infrastructures it will associate with, including the European Open Science Cloud and the European Health Data Space (and other data spaces). Industry clearly calls for a role for 1+MG to provide clear recommendations to the field on data standards for data and for data integration systems/platforms, while the oncology community realises there will be a need for practical data standards simple enough to be used by medics while including all required information.

Discussions on the infrastructure requirements for 1+MG showed a clear need across use case areas to connect research and care. On the one hand there is a need to support a wide variety of analyses, growing in complexity with other data sources, including future deeper phenotypic and lifestyle data related to personalised health. On the other hand there was a call to help standardise data management tools, support standard analytics workflows for genomics-based diagnostics in the clinic (e.g. in oncology) and to offer guidelines for tool providers to plug their analytics platforms to the 1+MG infrastructure. It is clearly recommended that 1+MG is being established as a FAIR-based infrastructure, supporting rich and machine-interoperable metadata standards. Given the fact that data in this 'space' will not be centralised, it is recommended to explore how its federated structure can support federated analysis by facilitating data-visiting approaches to help shared data access without data leaving the organisation.

The session presenting and discussing the Genome of Europe project as part of 1+MG received a lot of attention. Although it has been designed to be an integral part of the 1+MG infrastructure, its focus on data from population cohorts without clinical bias and its role as overall genetic reference collection make it a special case under the 1+MG umbrella. The GoE-data may not be generated in healthcare, but once established the collection will serve as a reference to all

disease area's, providing crucial information on the basic European genetic makeup. Debate in this session about the phenotypic data to be included can be well understood from a general vision to realise clinically actionable datasets, and from the vision of the future of enhanced data analysis covering multi-source data types, including multi-omics, imaging and exposome data. 1+MG will need to provide a way to allow future linkage of associated data elements from national health data records even if they have not been incorporated into the Genome of Europe collection.

7. Conclusions

Recommendations from the use case breakouts can be summarised as listed below and they have been communicated to the working groups in 1+MG and corresponding work packages in B1MG. The general recommendations related to the design of 1+MG have been input for the overall design of 1+MG and its relation to e.g. the European Health Data Space. The table below lists the recommendations per use case.

Use case WGs	ELSI	Data Standards	Infrastructure	General
WG8 Rare Diseases	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Consent: Guidance to re-consent & use of flexible consent forms; 2. Defining & harmonising terminologies & ethical concerns 	Include quality standards developed for WES data.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Multiple access levels needed for queries in healthcare (e.g., diagnosis) and research (e.g., identification of a new disease gene). 2. Inclusion/usage of imaging data for discovery/matching 	
WG9 Cancer	Standardised workflows needed with data protection impact assessment	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Multiple ontologies for oncology data 2. Cost for licences of e.g. SNOMED are a hurdle 3. Cancer has longitudinal aspect (multiple data points in time) 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Need for a synthetic dataset for cancer genomes 2. Work towards standardised cancer data analysis software 	
WG10 Common Complex	1. Return of data to the participant?	Need FAIRification of lifestyle/phenotypic	Distributed analysis across data hubs to	

Diseases	(Data communication/ visualisation) 2. Different approach for polygenic risk scores (PRS) required 3. Inclusivity in healthcare as minority groups are often excluded	data	generate PRS must be supported	
WG11 Infectious diseases	1. Different interpretation of ethical issues for different use cases/populations (pathogens, patients) 2. Provision of a code of conduct (effects of GDPR on governance structures)	1. Build capacity in the use of community-developed standards to drive harmonisation and standardisation of (meta-)data 2. Implement machine readable DMPs that collect data on components of FAIR	1. Need to collect & link host + pathogen data - connect relevant communities 2. Need to locate data properly - through disciplinary platforms, beyond projects	
WG12 Genome of Europe	1. Define legal context of data from population cohorts outside healthcare 2. Minorities: Genetic non-discriminatory act needed in all participating countries - include in minimal requirements	Define very minimal dataset and associated standard ontologies.	Multiple use cases to support (value of a reference for everything), different infrastructure requirements. Dependent upon depth of associated phenotypes.	
WG7 Industry Engagement	1. Need for practical (re-)consent for secondary use of	Clear recommendations needed on common data	Enable data-visiting approaches that help in sharing data to other stakeholders	1. Industry involvement is crucial for putting (genomics) data into clinical

	<p>health data, including in clinical studies.</p> <p>2. Address (lack of) public trust in genomic/health data sharing and implementation of new health technologies such as genomics (and AI).</p>	<p>standards and standards for data integration systems/platforms</p>	<p>without data leaving the organisation.</p>	<p>practice and routine</p> <p>2. Industry is willing to co-create with academia, with regards to standards, access procedures, privacy by design, quality and interoperability</p> <p>3. Big changes in healthcare system are taking place, industry is also willing to feed back (consented) data to (national) data repositories</p> <p>4. In the future we need to combine personal/patient data to get to predictive and outcome-based reimbursement systems and improve patient outcomes (beyond the scope of 1+MG?) at a country level</p>
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8. Follow up and Impact

All in all the SF 2021 has been an excellent instrument to capture the broad expert input from stakeholders across Europe in further developing the 1+MG and B1MG workstreams set up to realise the 1+MG goals.

The recommendations have been shared with the colleagues in the 1+MG working groups on ELSI, Standards and Infrastructure actively present during the SF and close after the meeting, and have since been taken up by these teams together with the coordination team to seed the design of the further roadmap for the 1+MG working groups.

Critically, the discussions and recommendations have greatly contributed to the design of the proposal under the Digital Europe Programme for establishing the Genomics Data Infrastructure (GDI) for 1+MG and led to the formation of broad project consortium that started Q4 2022 with

substantial support from the European Commission (DG-CNECT) to realise the infrastructure for 1+MG in the coming years.

10. Annex

Annex 1 Agenda and minutes of the online SF 2021

B1MG Stakeholder Meeting Agenda Wednesday, 17th November 2021

Meeting Location Details:

B1MG Stakeholder Meeting. 10:00 -17:00 CET (09:00 - 16:00 GMT) connection opens at 09:30 CET

Goal: Gain stakeholder feedback and recommendations across all use cases on elements of the 1+MG Trust Framework

Today's [minutes](#)

Location: Virtual meeting - Please note that this meeting will be recorded

Dial-in details:

<https://elixir-europe-org.zoom.us/j/85274955482?pwd=c1N2ZVlp1bmU1ZE9jTlI0dktNaUJZz09>

Meeting ID: 852 7495 5482

Passcode: 485337

Support contact: B1MG-Coordination@elixir-europe.org

Note: The times in the agenda are **CET**

9:30 10:00	Arrival & registration (waiting room open for virtual participants)
10:00	Welcome (Serena Scollen)
10:05 11:00	Introduction to the Trust Framework (Chairs: Ruben Kok & Serena Scollen) <ul style="list-style-type: none">• ELSI aspects of the Trust Framework: Regina Becker• Data standards and data quality aspects: Jeroen Belien• Infrastructure aspects: Tommi Nyronen
	Discussion

	<p>Go to www.menti.com from your phone or computer and enter the code OR scan the QR Code to start participating in today's meeting polls.</p> <p>6558 7815</p>
<p>11:00 11:15</p>	<p>Coffee Break</p>
<p>11:15 12:15</p>	<p>Presentation from the European Commission: Szymon Bielecki, DG CNECT</p> <p>“Public trust and engagement: challenges for genomics and its implementation in health care” Carla van El, Department of Human Genetics, AmsterdamUMC, NL</p> <p>Discussion</p> <p>General introduction to the afternoon programme</p>
<p>12:15 13:00</p>	<p>Lunch break</p>
<p>13:00 14:45</p>	<p>Use case workshops (per disease area, workshops in parallel)</p> <p>GOAL: list of recommendations to thematic WGs/WPs from use case perspective to be discussed adopted in the work processes of these WP's</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rare Diseases (WG8) Chairs: Marco Tartaglia & Sergi Beltran <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ERN-ITHACA and the Rare Disease landscape in Europe (Klea Vyshka, Robert Debré University Hospital, Paris, FR) • The Screen4Care EU-IMI project: aims and vision (Alessandra Ferlini, S.Anna University Hospital & University of Ferrara, Ferrara, IT) • Solve-RD (Lisenka Vissers, Radboud University Medical Center, Nijmegen, NL) • GenoMed4ALL (Federico Álvarez, Universidad Politécnica de Madrid, Madrid, ES) • EJP RD (Annalisa Landi, Fondazione per la Ricerca Farmacologica Gianni Benzi Onlus, Bari, IT) • Cancer (WG9) Chairs: Giovanni Tonon & Nina Habermann <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • GHGA - Jan Korbel (EMBL, Heidelberg) • EUCANCan/ICGC-ARGO - David Torrents, (BSC, Barcelona) • Common and complex diseases (WG10) Chairs: Andres Metspalu & Serena Scollen

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The FinnGen-study - Mervi Aavikko (University of Helsinki) • PerMed project in Estonia: delivering genomics based health care - Lili Milani (UTARTU) • Synthetic genome data simulation project - Tero Hiekkalinna (National Institute of Health and Welfare, Finland) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Infectious Diseases (WG11) Chairs: Katja Kivinen & Emanuela Oldoni <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The COVID-19 Data Portal - Guy Cochrane (EMBL-EBI) • ISIDORE project - Romain David (ERINHA) • BY-COVID project - Katharina Lauer (ELIXIR Hub) • EC COVID-19 workshop series - Lauren Maxwell (Heidelberg Institute for Global Health) • Industry (WG7) Chairs: Silja Elunurm & Merlijn van Rijswijk <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Perspective of the Estonian Biobank why Industry Involvement is crucial and a introduction to the work of the Industry involvement working group - Silja Elunurm (Estonian Ministry of Social Affairs, WG 7 1+MG) • Genomics as part of the health research puzzle: industry view - Danny van Roijen (Digital Health Director, Cocir) • Personalized Healthcare why data skills are crucial to get there - Wendy Maas (Policy Lead Personalised Healthcare, Roche The Netherlands) • Genome of Europe (WG12) Chairs: André Uitterlinden & Ruben Kok <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • WG12 status update - André Uitterlinden (Erasmus MC)
14:45 15:00	Wrap-up from workshops
15:00 15:15	Coffee Break
15:15- 15:45	Report from the workshops WGLs (5 mins per presentation)
15:45 -16:15	General Discussion on the outcomes of the workshops and recommendations on the Trust Framework
16:15 16:30	Wrap-up with the WPLs of the morning session (Ruben Kok & Serena Scollen)
16:30	Meeting ends

